

Pharmacist Interventions for Non-cancer Pain: A Protocol for a Scoping Review

This protocol followed the Unified Management, Assessment and Review of Information (SUMARI) guidelines and template from the Joanna Briggs Institute

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Abstract

Objective: With this scoping review, we aim to identify existing (clinical) pharmacist interventions for patients with chronic non-cancer pain (CNCP)

Introduction: CNCP is a highly prevalent burden associated with a number of comorbidities. Therefore, CNCP is complex and difficult to handle. Gold standard for the treatment of CNCP is a multi-modal approach, including interprofessional health care providers like medical doctors, physiotherapists, nurses and pharmacists. The scope and content of existing pharmacist interventions in CNCP is, however, unclear.

Methods: We will follow the PRISMA extension for scoping reviews. The search strategy will be composed of the two thematic blocks 'Pharmacists' and 'Chronic Non-Cancer Pain'. We will search Medline, Embase and PsycInfo via Ovid, CINAHL via EBSCO and the Cochrane Library. Both title and abstract screening and full-text screening will be performed by two independent reviewers. Data extraction will be performed by one reviewer and validated by a second. The screening and extraction process will take place in April and May 2023.

Ethics and dissemination: No ethics approval was sought as only publicly available literature will be searched. The review will be disseminated in a peer-reviewed journal and presented at congresses.

Introduction

Chronic non-cancer pain (CNCP) is a highly prevalent burden. A recent review estimated the prevalence to be around 51% in high-income countries.[1] Data specific to Switzerland is, however, scarce.[2] A telephone-based survey among the Swiss population (median age 48), showed a prevalence of chronic pain in 19%. Internationally, a prevalence of 12% in Spain and up to 30% in Norway was reported.[3] Another study estimated a one-month prevalence of moderate to severe CNCP in Europe to be 19%.[4]

The economic implications of CNCP are also largely unclear: A 2007 study estimated direct and indirect cost at around 2.9 - 5.8 billion CHF.[2] The calculation of costs was extrapolated from German and British data and, therefore, remains somewhat of a rough estimate. Moreover, this absolute amount is likely to be larger today as might be reflected by mounting expenses for health care.[5]

CNCP is associated with a number of comorbidities and risk factors: Among the most frequent are depression and insomnia.[6-8] The effect of age on CNCP remains a topic of discussion and results of different studies vary. At times, age is associated with less CNCP, while it peaks during middle age.[9] Others have argued that age exhibits no influence.[10] Age having a positive correlation to CNCP was, however, also reported, especially due to higher multi-morbidity.[11, 12] In addition, dementia and cognitive decline are diagnosed more often in older people. These conditions make pain assessment more difficult and complex.[13] Furthermore, CNCP is associated with female sex and gender.[14, 15] A number of other influencing factors such as an unhealthy life-style (obesity, smoking, alcohol consumption), poor socio-economic background and unemployment may have a negative impact on CNCP.[16-20] Contrarily, physical activity, balanced nutrition, sunshine and vitamin D as well as active coping strategies are found to be beneficial to CNCP.[21-24] It is clear that CNCP is a complex syndrome and its implications manifold.

Due to CNCP's complexity, therapy is often demanding and should be based on a multi-modal approach.[25] Interventions provided by pharmacists have been shown to be effective in managing CNCP by providing education to patients or by performing various forms of medication reviews.[26, 27] However, it remains unclear, what these interventions entail and what their scope is. With this review, we aim to shed light on different (clinical) pharmacy practices addressing CNCP.

Review question

What are the characteristics (including scope, quality, involved professions) of existing pharmacist interventions for the therapy of CNCP?

Keywords

Chronic non-cancer pain; Pharmacists; Medication review; Patient education

Inclusion Criteria & Exclusion Criteria

We will include articles, if they comply with the criteria listed in table 1.

Table 1 Inclusion and exclusion criteria for the literature review

PICOS	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Population	Adults (> 18 years) Chronic non cancer pain: Pain of any aetiology lasting longer than 3 months or author-defined pain as chronic	Children (<18 years) Chronic cancer pain Acute pain (<3 months) or author defined as acute pain
Intervention	Any pharmacist intervention delivered in any setting (i.e. hospital, community pharmacy, long	

	term care) with pharmacist as the leader or with/without an interprofessional team	
Control	Any or no comparator	
Outcomes	All reported outcomes: Pain related: Pain intensity, pain interference Health related: Quality of life, mental health Medication related: change in medication, Potentially inappropriate medications (PIMs) Institutional: patient satisfaction, guidelines used Economic: cost effectiveness	
Study Design	All primary literature	Conference abstracts, proceeding papers editorials, commentaries, literature reviews
Other	Inclusion Criteria	Exclusion Criteria
Language	All languages	

Methods

Search strategy

The search strategy will be built up in two blocks covering ‘Pharmacists’ and ‘Chronic Non-Cancer Pain’. The two blocks will be combined with the logical operator ‘AND’. Within a block, we will combine free-text terms as well as indexing terms (i.e. MeSH, Emtree, Subject Headings). The search strategy will be validated for Medline via Ovid in collaboration with the medical library of the University of Basel. Afterwards, the search strategy will be translated to work in Embase and PsycInfo via Ovid, CINAHL via EBSCO and the Cochrane Library using the Systematic Review Accelerator.[28]

The validated search strings can be found in the appendix.

Data management and Screening process

The articles found by the validated search string will be downloaded and uploaded to Covidence® (Covidence systematic review software, Veritas Health Innovation, Melbourne, Australia. Available at www.covidence.org), where we will deduplicate the articles.

After deduplication, we will perform title-abstract and full-text screening independently by two reviewers using Covidence. Conflicts will be resolved by consensus. We will use the PRISMA extension for scoping reviews for reporting.[29]

Data extraction

The following information will be extracted in Covidence by one reviewer and checked by a second: Authors, year of publishing, country of origin, study design, setting, objectives, methods, type of pharmacist intervention, guidelines used for intervention, characteristics of pharmacist intervention, outcomes, results and conclusions.

Data Analysis and Presentation

Data extracted will be presented in a table format and as a narrative synthesis. We aim to give a semi-quantitative overview of different interventions. Moreover, we will perform a subgroup analysis according to patient age (18-65 vs >65 years).

Funding

We received no external funding.

Conflict of Interest

We declare no conflict of interest

Dissemination

We will submit the scoping review to a peer-reviewed academic journal when completed. Additionally, we will present the results at scientific congresses.

Acknowledgements

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Appendix

Medline via Ovid	
Chronic pain	exp chronic pain/ or ((chronic or persistent or relentless or enduring or constant or sustained or continuous or lingering or protracted or life-long or continual or continuing or recurrent or recurring) adj4 (pain or ache* or cramp* or spasm* or colic* or sore* or tender* or burn* or arthralgia or headache or earache or migraine or mastodynia or allodynia or neuralgia or hyperalgesia or '*myalgia')).ti,ab.
Pharmacists	exp Pharmacists/ or exp Pharmacy Service, Hospital/ or exp Community Pharmacy Services/ or exp Pharmacy/ or exp Evidence-Based Pharmacy Practice/ or exp Pharmaceutical Services/ or (('pharmaceutical' adj2 service\$') or 'pharmaceutical care' or pharmacies* or pharmacy* or pharmacist*).ti,ab.
Combined string	(exp chronic pain/ or ((chronic or persistent or relentless or enduring or constant or sustained or continuous or lingering or protracted or life-long or continual or continuing or recurrent or recurring) adj4 (pain or ache* or cramp* or spasm* or colic* or sore* or tender* or burn* or arthralgia or headache or earache or migraine or mastodynia or allodynia or neuralgia or hyperalgesia or '*myalgia')).ti,ab.) and (exp Pharmacists/ or exp Pharmacy Service, Hospital/ or exp Community Pharmacy Services/ or exp Pharmacy/ or exp Evidence-Based Pharmacy Practice/ or exp Pharmaceutical Services/ or (('pharmaceutical' adj2 service\$') or 'pharmaceutical care' or pharmacies* or pharmacy* or pharmacist*).ti,ab.)